

Comparison Between Quantum Spatial and Temporal Interactions

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The notion of temporal and spatial interactions exists in Newtonian mechanics and we suggest it is useful to compare the two as they differ even though time and x are both considered co-ordinates of spacetime. In particular, space has two directions for every spatial co-ordinate (positive and negative) and so one may move backwards in space. This is associated with a force which may be positive or negative. Even though one may write a spatial equation in terms of energy, if kinetic energy becomes zero due to a negative force, then after this, the particle moves in the negative direction. As a result, one has a potential or interaction energy $V(x)$ which is linked to force = $-\text{grad } V(r)$. (We only consider $V(x)$, not $V(x,t)$ here).

Things are different with interactions which take place in time only, even though these too may be considered in terms of energy. In general, these seem to be more statistical in nature. In particular, a bound system may absorb a photon. This is an interaction in time, but all subsequent interactions are in increasing time. There is no going backwards in time. An excited state may lose energy or gain more energy. There is an interaction, but no force backwards in time. In such a case, the energy of the photons is their state energy, while $V(x)$ is not a state energy of the system creating it. For example, a charged particle has a $V(r) = -kq/r$, but its state energy is $.5 e_0 \text{ Electric field} \cdot \text{Electric field}$, where $\text{Electric field} = -\text{grad } V(r)$. One may already see differences in time interactions in classical statistical mechanics even if a $V(x)$ exists.

As a result, of the differences between positive and negative motion in x and only positive motion in t , one may have a localized particle in space and this leads to boundary conditions which yield discrete energy levels. At the same time, a distribution in free particles p 's in the wavefunction $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$ leads to a spatial distribution $W^*(x)W(x)$. At the same time, interactions in time (with photons for example), lead to a distribution in atom states in the wavefunction, $W(x,t) = \text{Sum over } n \ \exp(-En/T) W_n(x)$ and a time distribution $\text{Integral } dx \ W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$.

Spatial Interactions in Newtonian Mechanics

Space and time are co-ordinates in special relativity, but one may move backwards and forwards in x , but only forwards in time. We suggest that this leads to consequences in various physical problems. Newtonian mechanics is largely interested in spatial interactions and so a vector p (momentum) is introduced to describe motion in both directions in x , even though the concept of kinetic energy $p \cdot p/2m$ exists and is the same for both directions. What this means, we suggest, is that given kinetic energy:

$$P \cdot p/2m \quad ((1))$$

there is more information hidden in expression ((1)) than meets the eye. ((1)) is a rotational scalar which allows for p and $-p$ vector solutions, suggesting both forwards and backwards motion. Physically, there must be a way to increase p for a particle moving to the right and increase $-p$ for a particle moving to the left. This suggests that the physical process which

increases -p would decrease p, which is proportional to v. v is a measure of the motion through x relative to t and one may have motion both forward and backwards in x.

$$v = dx/dt \quad ((2))$$

One may also define

$$v\text{-time} = dt/[dx] \quad ((3))$$

The catch is that [dx] must be positive even if one moves backwards in space, because one may only move forwards in time. As a result, there is no sense of a force acting in the backwards direction in time.

In space, however, one may have force which slows down a positive v (velocity) until it stops. Then it is accelerated in the negative direction. Given such a force, if it is conservative, it may be mathematically written as:

$$F = - \text{grad } V(r) \quad ((4))$$

V(r) at this point is simply a math function. One may, however, describe spatial motion in terms of energy in Newtonian mechanics and obtain:

$$p \text{ dot } p / 2m + V(r) = E \quad ((5))$$

Given that a force may slow down a particle going in one direction, stop it and reverse its motion, and the mirror process may occur in the negative x region, one may localize a particle in space.

V(r) in ((5)) has units of energy, but we ask: Is this a state energy of the system creating the V(r)? p dot p / 2m is a state energy of the moving particle. ((5)) is a conservation equation showing that even though a particle loses its state kinetic energy, it is as if it has a state potential energy such that the sum is a constant E. From a point of view of measurement using a target at x (which does not interact with V(x)), the target is only interested in p for impulse hits. We suggest that V(r) is an interaction energy which pertains to the interacting particle and is not a state energy of the system creating V(r)

A particular example is that of a charged particle which has:

$$V(r) = kq/r \quad ((6a)) \quad \text{with Electric field} = -\text{grad } V(r) \quad ((6b))$$

and

$$\text{Self-energy} = .5 \epsilon_0 \text{ Electric field dot Electric field} \quad ((7))$$

The state energy of the charge creating V(r) is ((7)) not V(r). V(r) is associated with work done on an interacting charge, an interaction energy. In other words:

Interaction energy = $q_1 V(r)$ where q_1 is the interacting charge ((8))

$V(r)$ without q_1 is essentially irrelevant (in many cases) while interaction action is not. It represents the work done assembling q , each dq at a time and so is state energy. We belabour this point, because spatial interactions are quite different from purely temporal ones.

Temporal Interactions

Consider the case of a box with photons such that the total energy is E_{total} . One would ascribe a temperature T to such a box. If one adds a ground state atom with energy:

Constant+ E_0 ((9))

(with T remaining essentially the same), then this atom may absorb photons and then emit them etc. This represents an interaction in time, but there is no force slowing down the atom in time or reversing the order of time. The energy of the photon is used in the interaction, but unlike $V(r)$, it also represents the state energy of the photon. One then has a probabilistic problem because given a state E_1 , one does not know if it will drop to a lower state or absorb a photon and move to a higher one. This then becomes a statistical problem because one must ask: What is the probability for the atom to have an energy level of E_n , assuming a discrete set of E_n values?

To solve this problem, one may consider a problem with two atoms. If one argues that:

$P_1(E_1) P_2(E_2) = P_3(E_3) P_4(E_4)$ where $E_1 + E_2 = E_3 + E_4$ ((10))

Then: $P(E) = C \exp(-E/T)$ i.e. the Maxwell-Boltzmann (M|B) distribution ((11))

Given that one has the MB distribution in ((11)), we consider a second example, namely that of an MB gas with a potential $V(x)$. We argued in the previous section that $V(x)$ is associated with a force which may slow down a particle and then reverse its direction. This leads to a picture of motion in time. An MB gas, however, is an equilibrium in time, just like the excited atom example above. In any tiny dx region, one has a certain number of particles and a temperature T . These particles follow ((10)) regardless of the value of $V(x)$ at dx . At another dx at x_2 , one must have the same T for thermal equilibrium and so whatever particles are there must also follow ((11)). If $V(x)$ were not present, one would have the same spatial density, i.e. the same number of particles at x_1 and x_2 . This suggests that given $V(x)$, one might have different numbers of particles at each x point, i.e. different pressures. Imagine that $V(x)=0$ at x_1 and that there exist $N(x_1)$ particles. In moving to x_2 (for a $V(x)$ associated with a slowing force), one has:

$.5mv_1^2$ at $x_1 = .5mv_2^2 + V(x_2)$ ((12))

by conservation of energy.

The probability for ((12)), however, is still $\exp(-.5mv_1^2) = \exp(-.5mv_2^2/T + V(x_2)/T)$. ((13))

Given that $\exp(-.5mv^2/T)$ is the MB factor for T, then $\exp(-V(x)/T)$ must be a density in space factor.

This statistical problem focuses mainly on energy considerations and not on a particle slowing down, stopping and reversing its direction in space. It seems that interactions in time are linked with a statistical approach which is based on energy, while spatial interactions (a bound or trapped particle) must make reference to motion in both x directions and so energy of $V(x)$ is an interaction energy which is directly linked to a force which can change the direction of motion. We note that $V(x)$ in the MB case does contain some spatial features, but one does not consider a particle slowing down and then reversing its direction as in a single particle bound state.

Quantum Mechanical Considerations

We try to apply these ideas to quantum mechanics. We first consider a single particle bound state with

$$KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((14))$$

Given the spatial nature of this problem, even though one only has energy in ((14)), classically there is motion in one direction and then the opposite such that the particle is bound or localized. This is an important idea which carries over to quantum mechanics in the form of the boundary condition:

$$W(x) = \text{wavefunction} = 0 \text{ at } x = \text{infinite and } x = -\text{infinite} \quad ((15))$$

Such a boundary condition does not exist in a purely temporal interaction as we will argue. This boundary condition has important consequences.

A free particle in quantum mechanics is described by complex probability $\exp(ipx)$ so that:

$$KE_{ave}(x) = \left\{ \sum \text{over } p \ a(p) \ p^2/2m \ \exp(ipx) \right\} / \left\{ \sum \text{over } p \ a(p) \ \exp(ipx) \right\} \quad ((16))$$

If the denominator of ((16)) is denoted by $W(x)$, then

$$KE_{ave}(x) = -1/2m \ d/dx \ dW/dx / W \quad ((17))$$

$\exp(ipx)$ represents a single p value which is linked with an energy $p^2/2m$. A quantum free particle would be described by the overall probability:

$$\exp(-ipp/2mt + ipx) \quad ((18))$$

Why isn't $\exp(-i t \ p^2/2m)$ incorporated into $KE_{ave}(x)$? Formally,

$$W_n(x,t) = \exp(-i E_n t) W(x) \quad ((19))$$

Why is E_n used in ((19)), where E_n is a discrete energy value which follows from the boundary conditions ((15))? We suggest that even though $\exp(ipx)$ is a solution of:

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d^2 W}{dx^2} / W = p^2/2m \quad ((20))$$

This completely ignores the ensemble average interaction with $V(x)$ which is key to the bound state. In such a case, the statistical equation which applies to $\exp(ipx) = W(x)$ is actually:

$$a(p) p^2/2m \exp(ipx) + \sum_k V(k) a(p-k) \exp(ikx) \exp(i(p-k)x) = a(p) E_n \quad ((21))$$

$$\text{where } V(x) = \sum_k V(k) \exp(ikx) \quad ((22))$$

In ((21)), the energy associated with $\exp(ipx)$ is E_n and hence $\exp(-iE_n t)$. ((23))

There exists a distribution in x due to:

$$P(x) = W^*(x)W(x) \quad ((24)) \text{ due to a momentum distribution in } W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$$

If one considers a time interaction, one has a photon gas with temperature T interacting with an atom. The total energy is E_{total} , but that is not particularly interesting. One has in this case:

$$W(x,t) = \sum_n \exp(-E_n/T) W_n(x) \quad ((25)) \text{ and}$$

$$P(t) = \int dx W^*(x,t)W(x,t) \quad ((26))$$

Similar to $P(x)$, one has a distribution in t because one has a distribution in E . There is not restriction on T because there are no boundary conditions.

Thus, there are similarities between the purely spatial interaction and the purely temporal one in terms of the particle having a spatial density in one case and temporal ones in the other.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we point out that even though x and t are spacetime co-ordinates, there are differences between purely spatial and purely temporal interactions because a particle may move in two directions in x , but only in one in t . This leads to the notion of a force related to an interaction energy (potential multiplied by charge or density) in space, while energy interactions in a purely temporal case can be linked with a state energy of the entity creating the interactions in the temporal case. For example, photon energies excite atoms. In another temporal example, however, a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, $V(x)$ appears solely as an interacting energy, but does not represent the state energy of the system creating $V(x)$. This example, however, does bring in space and so is not purely temporal.

We argue, however, that there is a commonality to spatial and temporal interactions. For the spatial case, one has a distribution in space $W^*(x)W(x)$ due to a distribution in momentum, $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. In the temporal case, one has a distribution in energy: $W(x,t) = \sum_n \exp(-E_n/T) W_n(x)$ and a temporal distribution $\int dx W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$.